

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

First, allow me to gratefully thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. Second, I'd like to encourage researchers to join our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. Finally, we are always interested in high quality proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends. If you have an interesting proposal, please contact me at cguetl@tugraz.at.

In this regular issue, I am very glad to introduce four accepted high quality papers from authors of four different countries.

Jorge Luis Victória Barbosa, Bruno Kucera Sempé, Bruno Mota and Leandro Infantini Dini from Brasil introduce their research and findings on an anesthesia alert system based on dynamic profiles inferred through the medical history of patients. Based on 71 academic studies, Ulas Gulec, Murat Yilmaz, and Veysi Isler from Turkey focus in their research to explore potential software development activities and determine whether designing a specific software development methodology for VR projects is beneficial. Akrivi Krouska, Christos Troussas and Maria Virvou from Greece evaluate in their work the applicability and accuracy of five commonly used learning-based classifiers (Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, k- Nearest Neighbor, Logistic Regression and C4.5) and the lexicon-based approach (SentiStrength) has been evaluated for Twitter Sentiment Analysis. Last but not least, Arthur F. Pinto, Ricardo Terra, Eduardo Guerra and Fernando São Sabbas from Brazil address the specific shortcomings of architectural conformance tools by introducing an architectural conformance process into continuous integration.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: cguetl@iicm.edu